

**Mixed Ligand Complexes of Nickel(II)
Phthalate with Ligands containing Sulphur
and Nitrogen Donor Atoms**

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SHUKLA and coworkers¹⁻³ studied the mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) phthalates with aromatic and chelating amines and diamines. Here we report similar complexes of nickel(II) phthalate with sulphur and nitrogen donor ligands like naphthylthiourea, 1,10-phenanthroline, morpholine, 3,5-lutidine, piperidine and benzylamine.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by adding an excess of the ligands, morpholine, 3,5-lutidine, piperidine or benzylamine, to nickel phthalate in methanol at room temp. or by refluxing a solution of nickel phthalate in methanol with large excess of the ligands, 1,10-phenanthroline and naphthylthiourea for 2 hr. All the complexes were recrystallised from hot methanol and dried *in vacuo*.

Nickel was estimated as nickel dimethylglyoximate, nitrogen by using the method of Dumas and carbon and hydrogen by microanalysis. Conductance was measured in 10⁻³M nitrobenzene solution using Toshniwal conductivity bridge (Type CL 0102). The magnetic susceptibilities were determined using Gouy method. These data are given in Table 1. IR spectra in the range 4000-400 cm⁻¹ were recorded on a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer in nujol mull. The electronic spectra were recorded in chloroform using Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses show the molecular formulae of the complexes to be either Ni(phth)(L)₂

or Ni(phth)(L')₂, where L=1,10-phenanthroline and L'=naphthylthiourea, morpholine, 3,5-lutidine, piperidine or benzylamine. The reported molar conductance values of the complexes using the formula weight suggest them to be non-electrolytes. All the complexes are paramagnetic with μ_{eff} 3.0-3.2 B.M. which are within the expected range for the octahedral geometry of Ni(II) complexes³.

The ir spectra of the present mixed ligand complexes are, in general, very complex with many overlapping and unresolved bands. It is, therefore, rather difficult to pinpoint and assign the bands definitely. Nevertheless, by comparing the spectra of the complexes amongst themselves and with the available literature data, an attempt is made to arrive at the most probable metal-donor bonding sites.

In all the present complexes with nitrogen donor ligands (except the naphthylthiourea) the asymmetric and symmetric >COO stretches of the phthalyl moiety, in general, appear around 1600 and 1400 cm⁻¹, respectively. These bands in comparison with the corresponding bands (1580 and 1380 cm⁻¹, respectively) of the nickel(II) phthalate⁴ reactant and also with those of the corresponding sodium phthalate bands⁵, provide evidence for the bonding of both the phthalate anion (>C<O>M) and N-bonded amines to the metal ion^{4,5}. Further, the evidence of metal-oxygen bonding has also been provided by the occurrence of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ around 510 cm⁻¹⁶.

As regards the metal-nitrogen bonding in 1,10-phenanthroline complex, the bands at 1430 (>C=N)⁷, 840 and 720 cm⁻¹ (C-H out of plane vibration and ring stretching)⁸ frequencies compared to the respective free ligand frequencies (1626, 855 and 720 cm⁻¹)⁹ indicate that 1,10-phenanthroline appears to coordinate to the metal ion through both of its nitrogen atoms. Similarly, the bands at 3270

(νNH), 1130 ($\nu-\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{C}$) and 1010 ($\nu-\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$) cm⁻¹ compared to the corresponding bands (3325,

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINTS, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Compound	Colour	m.p. (°C)	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				Δ_M (mhos)	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Ni	N	O	H		
Ni(phth)(phen) ₂	Green	262	9.88 (10.08)	9.49 (9.61)	66.21 (65.95)	3.60 (3.45)	0.84	3.0
Ni(phth)(NTU) ₂	Green	207	5.58 (5.70)	10.69 (10.81)	60.80 (60.63)	3.80 (3.91)	0.76	3.1
Ni(phth)(moph) ₂	Green	>300	10.02 (10.28)	10.00 (9.81)	50.31 (50.47)	7.21 (7.05)	0.66	3.2
Ni(phth)(pip) ₂	Green	184	10.12 (10.43)	9.68 (9.92)	50.44 (50.71)	8.25 (8.37)	0.74	3.1
Ni(phth)(3,5-lut) ₂	Blue	>300	8.85 (9.01)	8.92 (8.57)	66.40 (66.18)	6.00 (6.17)	0.68	3.1
Ni(phth)(BA) ₂	Blue	142	8.91 (9.02)	8.64 (8.58)	66.84 (66.24)	6.82 (6.17)	0.72	3.2

1142 and 1110 cm^{-1}) of the free ligand morpholine¹⁰, is also indicative of morpholine coordination to the metal ion through its nitrogen.

More or less the same conclusion can be drawn on similar grounds for lutidine¹¹ and piperidine¹² mixed ligand complexes. However, for benzylamine complex, lack of far ir and ¹³C nmr data poses some problem. Nevertheless, comparing the ir spectra of this amine mixed ligand complex with those of other complexes and supplemented by its analytical data (Table 1), it leads one to conclude that benzylamine could also be coordinating to the metal ion through its nitrogen.

In the case of naphthylthiourea complex the bands⁵ at 1580 and 1380 cm^{-1} of the phthalate ion was found to be unchanged compared to that of the starting compound nickel phthalate, which clearly indicated the absence of metal-nitrogen bond formation in the naphthylthiourea complex. The absence of metal-nitrogen bond in the naphthylthiourea complex is also evident from the appearance of unchanged NH and NH₂ bands of the free ligand¹⁴. Besides, the lowering of the C-S stretching frequency from 775 of the free ligand to 770 cm^{-1} in the complex indicates reduced double bond character of the C=S bond which is indicative of the presence of metal-sulphur bond¹⁵ in addition to the metal-oxygen bonding of the phthalate anion.

For octahedral nickel(II) complexes usually three main bands are expected at 8000-13000 (ν_1), 14000-19000 (ν_2) and 25000-30000 (ν_3) cm^{-1} arising from $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{2g}$, $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$ (F) and $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}$ (P) transitions, respectively, in their electronic spectra. These absorption bands at ν_1 8.8-9, ν_2 14.5-15.5 and ν_3 25.4-25.7 kK regions were observed for the present complexes in their electronic spectra. Besides, the ratio of ν_3/ν_1 of the bands¹⁶ was found to be ~ 1.7 which also confirms the octahedral configuration for all the complexes around the metal ion.

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Electrochemical Studies on the Complexes of Cadmium(II) with Citrulline at D.M.E.

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CITRULLINE is of extreme importance in production of urea in the living body. Krebs and Henseleit¹ have shown that the synthesis of urea from ammonia and carbon dioxide in presence of intact liver tissues is markedly accelerated by the addition of citrulline. Except for a single reference of glass electrode studies by Perkins², there is no report on the chelate formation abilities of citrulline with cadmium(II) and hence the present investigation was undertaken.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. The solution of cadmium(II) was prepared by dissolving a weighted amount of A.R. cadmium nitrate in conductivity water. The solution was standardized as usual³. Lithium perchlorate was used to keep the ionic strength constant. Sodium salt of citrulline was used as complexing agent. The pH of solution was kept constant at 6.4 ± 0.1 . Other experimental conditions are the same as described earlier⁴.

Results and Discussion

The cathodic reduction of cadmium(II) was found to be reversible in citrulline medium as revealed by the straight line plots of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log i/i_d - i$. The result of these plots varies within 32 ± 1 mV showing two electron reduction. The diffusion controlled nature of reduction was confirmed by the proportionality of diffusion current to the square root of the effective height of mercury column. There is appreciable cathodic shift in half-wave potential of Cd(II) when test solutions containing different amount of citrulline were